

STUDY OF COMPLIANCE WITH THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE LAW AND OTHER NORMATIVE AND LEGAL DOCUMENTS IN THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL STATEMENTS OF TELECOMMUNICATION SYSTEM ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. The article presents the importance of telecommunication system enterprises in the development of the country's economy and the analysis of the main indicators representing the efficiency of activities in "Uzbektelecom" JSC, "Radiocommunication, Radio Broadcasting and Television Center" JSC and "Uzbekiston pochta" JSC.

Key words. Enterprise, telecommunications, efficiency, financial independence, return on assets, return on private equity, solvency.

Introduction

One of the aspects that the auditor should pay serious attention to during the audit of financial statements is the use of the requirements of current laws and other regulatory legal documents or the formation of the auditor's opinion about the activities of the audited entity taking into account their requirements. In order to regulate this issue in the audit activity, the international audit standard No. 250 "Consideration of laws and regulatory documents in the audit of financial statements" is considered the main normative document. determining the impact of other regulatory documents, the auditor's obligations to comply with laws and other regulatory documents during the audit, the procedure for the auditor to learn compliance with laws and other regulatory documents by the managers of the audited entity, the audited entity in the course of audits cases of non-compliance

with the requirements of the law and other regulatory documents or actions of the auditor when the existence of such a situation is suspected, cases of non-compliance with the requirements of the law and other regulatory documents by the audited entity or suspected of the existence of such a situation the procedure for forming an auditor's conclusion in cases, identifying and evaluating such cases in the auditor's examination in the auditor's work documents is explained in detail.

It is worth noting that the impact of the requirements of current laws and other regulatory documents on the financial statements of the audited entity during the audit must be serious as a conceptual basis, or the auditor should act in accordance with the norms of existing laws and other regulatory documents when conducting the audit. required. In our opinion, it is appropriate to divide the regulatory documents that have such an effect on the audit into the following two types:

1. Regulatory documents that reveal the content of the indicators reflected in the financial statements of the audited entity or regulate the procedures that directly affect the content of the financial statements. An example of this is the consequences of banks not complying with the requirements of regulatory documents regulating their activities. For example, the movement of funds of a bank client requires the preparation of specified documents and the implementation of settlement transactions, if these tasks are not performed, the main obligations between the bank and the client will not be fulfilled, etc.;

2. Regulatory documents related to the activity of the audited entity and used in the implementation of the activity, but do not directly affect the content of the financial report of the audited entity. An example of this is the issue of ensuring compliance with safety requirements and health regulations during the work process.

Failure to comply with the two categories of regulatory documents mentioned above can lead to the formation of a reliable auditor's opinion and

excessive expenses for the financial activity of the audited entity. Non-compliance of the audited entity and audit organization with the requirements of the current regulatory documents is considered to be the main responsibility of their management, and making such a mistake shows that the management does not understand the norms of the current regulatory and legal documents, is indifferent to the requirements of the regulatory documents. means that he is (bepisand) or does not understand his obligations.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Many foreign economists have conducted scientific research on creating the theoretical and methodological foundations of the audit evidence collection process and improving it. They include A. Arens, R. Adams, M. Benis, R. Dodge, D. R. Carmichael, Dj. Lobbeck and Dj. Robertson can be included. Some aspects of the topic were discussed by N.P. Barishnikov, N.T. Belukha, S.M. Bichkova, N.P. Kamishanov, J.A. Kevorkova, S.A. Stukova, V.P. Suys, among the economists-scientists of the CIS countries. Studied by A.A. Terekhov and A.D. Sheremet.

Economic scientists of the republic have partially studied these issues in the textbooks, monographs and training manuals being created, as well as in published scientific articles and theses. Among them, K.B. Akhmedyanov, R.D. Dusmuratov, A.K. Ibragimov, N.F. Karimov, A.A. Karimov, Z.T. Mamatov, S.U. Mehmonov, A.A. Ostonokulov, U.O. Sakhobov, M.M. Tulakhodjaeva, B.A. Hasanov, B.Q. Hamdamov, K.R. Hotamov, I.N. Koziev and I.I. Meliev, some theoretical and methodological bases of audit evidence collection aspects have been studied. It is worth noting that although the above studies have given general views on the topic, the issue of collecting audit evidence has not been studied as a separate object of scientific research and as a whole system. This requires conducting comprehensive scientific research on this topic and defining research tasks.

Research methodology

Methods such as induction and deduction, targeted development, systematic and comparative analysis, graphic representation, expert assessment and economic statistics were widely used in the development of scientifically based conclusions and recommendations based on the detailed analysis of the problem raised in the scientific article, the systematization of the analysis results.

In the course of the financial statement audit, the auditor is required to assess compliance with the applicable laws and regulations and assess the reliability of the studied financial statement indicators, whether they are formed in accordance with the requirements of these regulatory documents. In turn, the management of the audited entity undertakes to carry out its activities in accordance with the current laws and regulatory documents, including the formation of the value of financial reporting indicators in accordance with the requirements of the legal documents defining the requirements for their content, and undertakes to control it. The above-mentioned standard No. 250 is used by the auditor to determine the distortions in the financial statements due to the fact that the audited entity does not comply with the applicable laws and regulations. However, the auditor is not responsible for preventing the audited entity from not complying with these documents and its consequences, and he is not responsible for fully identifying such cases during audits. In this regard, the auditor's obligation is determined by the fact that the audited entity is responsible for providing assurance that there are no material misstatements due to fraud or error in the financial statements of the audited entity.

During the financial statement audit, the auditor is required to pay the main attention to compliance with the requirements of the conceptual framework for the formation of the financial statement. Until today, many foreign and domestic economists have been conducting research on the issue of the conceptual framework.

If the audited entity is not directly related to the activity, the cases of non-compliance with these norms are less observed and vice versa. In particular, the following normative-legal documents are currently in force in the audit practice of the republic and are widely used (Table 1).

Table 1

Regulatory and legal documents used in the auditing practice of Uzbekistan

№	Name of regulatory document	The date of adoption of the regulatory legal document
1	Law No. ORQ-677 on auditor activity	February 25, 2021
2	International standards of auditing	April 11, 2022
3	Resolution No. 171 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the regulation on the procedure for the recognition of international auditing standards for use in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan"	September 29, 2021
4	Order No. 56 of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the list of international certificates of accountants that serve as a basis for issuing and extending the term of the auditor's qualification certificate without passing the qualification exam"	August 4, 2021
5	Decision PQ-5210 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the auditor	May 5, 2021

	certification system"	
6	Resolution No. 280 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the system of training employees of the internal audit service"	December 15, 2018
7	Annex 1 of Resolution No. 3101 "Regulations of Internal Control for Audit Organizations to Combat Money Laundering, Financing of Terrorism, and Financing of Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction"	September 19, 2018
8	Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3946 "On measures to further develop auditing activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan"	October 9, 2013
9	Appendix 2 of the order of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2515 entitled "Rules for filling out the information form on audit activity"	September 28, 2022
10	Resolution No. 538 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the regulation on the procedure for external control of the quality of work of the auditing organization"	The date of adoption of the regulatory legal document

The auditor is required to pay the main attention to the following aspects when assessing whether the audited entity complies with the norms of the current law and statutory documents:

- the existence of laws and other regulatory documents (conceptual framework) regulating the activity of the audited entity and the preparation and presentation of the financial report on the entity's activities, as well as the content of their regulatory and legal requirements;

- compliance of the audited entity with the requirements of the law and regulatory documents regulating its activity.

On the other hand, in order to form an auditor's opinion on the above issues, it is necessary to collect sufficient evidence confirming that the audited subject is complying with the law and regulatory documents. In our opinion, it is appropriate to perform the following audit procedures to clarify this issue:

1. Conducting a survey of the company's management or relevant officials on whether they use legal and statutory norms in their activities.

2. Studying the correspondence of the audited entity with licensing or law enforcement bodies on legal issues or evaluating their relationship to the activity of the audited entity, etc.

In the course of the audit, the auditor is required to receive written explanations from the heads of the company or relevant officials regarding the violations of the norms of the law and statutory regulations in their activities for the period of the audited financial statements, and to clarify the reasons for non-compliance with the norms. If the auditor has information about non-compliance or suspicion of non-compliance with the requirements of the current regulatory legal documents by the management of the audited entity or relevant officials, it is required to study the following:

- to study the reasons for non-compliance and the existence of supporting evidence;

- studying the impact (consequences) of non-compliance with regulatory and legal documents on the indicators of the enterprise's financial report and other information for the purpose of its evaluation.

Article 9 of the current "Law on audit activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan" stipulates that audit activities should be carried out primarily in accordance with laws and regulations that do not conflict with the legislation of Uzbekistan and the standards of audit activities. Also, the current international standards No. 800 "Special issues - audit of financial statements prepared in accordance with special purpose bases" and No. 720

"Responsibility of the auditor in relation to other information in the documents containing the audited financial statements" in this matter, the duties of the auditor and o learning standards are set. In particular, these standards emphasize the expediency of testing compliance with the requirements of normative legal documents in the activity of the subject under investigation. It is worth noting that since telecommunication system enterprises, which are the object of research, are considered state enterprises, it is possible to analyze the state of compliance with the norms of other regulatory and legal documents related to the characteristics of the state enterprises during the audit of financial statements. On the other hand, the auditor should gather sufficient evidence to justify the disclosure of the value of the financial statement representing the consequences of the violation of the requirements (conditions) of the above regulatory legal documents and their impact on the financial activity of the enterprise, and form his opinion in accordance with these evidence. In particular, in the enterprise that we conducted research, in particular, in the telecommunication system enterprises that we conducted research, it is appropriate to study the state of compliance with the following regulatory and legal documents during the audit of financial statements (Table 2).

Table 2

Normative legal documents used in the process of auditing financial statements of telecommunication system enterprises

№	Name of regulatory document	Date of regulatory document
1	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Radio Frequency	December 25,

	Spectrum". Tashkent, No. 725-I. https://www.lex.uz	1998
2	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Telecommunications". Tashkent, No. 822-I, https://www.lex.uz	August 20, 1999
3	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Information". Tashkent, No. 560-II, https://www.lex.uz	December 11, 2003
4	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Postal Communication". Tashkent, O'RQ-777, https://www.lex.uz	June 9, 2022
5	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Document Circulation". Tashkent, No. 560-II, https://www.lex.uz	April 29, 2004
6	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Digital Signature". Tashkent, O'RQ-793, https://www.lex.uz	October 12, 2022
7	Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Communication". Tashkent, No. 512-XII, https://www.lex.uz	January 13, 1992

In addition, telecommunication system enterprises use the calculation of the important indicators of efficiency specified in the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 28, 2015 No. 207 "On the introduction of criteria for evaluating the efficiency of the activities of joint-stock companies and other economic entities with a share of the state" during the audit of financial statements.

CONCLUSIONS

If the management of the enterprise does not take measures to eliminate the consequences of non-compliance with the requirements of the regulatory

documents identified by the auditor, the auditing organization may report the detected situation to the supervisory or law enforcement bodies, notifying the management of the enterprise. Although the auditor violates the principle of confidentiality, compliance with regulatory legal documents is more important than violating this principle and is the duty of the auditor. It may be appropriate for the auditor to discuss (consult) this situation with a legal expert of the auditing organization. Since most of the telecommunications system, which is the object of research, are state-owned enterprises, in this case, the auditor must inform the supervisory or law enforcement authorities of the cases of violation of the regulatory legal document. It is expedient for the auditor to obtain copies of each of the supporting documents or to discuss the identified cases with the management of the enterprise or relevant responsible persons regarding the compliance of the enterprise with the requirements of the current regulatory legal documents.

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